

Thermodynamic properties of binary liquid mixtures of 2-methoxyethanol with different amines at 308.15 K^ψ

M. Eswari Bai, K. G. Neerajakshi, K. S. V. Krishna Rao, G. Narayana Swamy and M. C. S. Subha*

Department of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, India

E-mail : mcsubha@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-8554-255244

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Densities and viscosities of the binary liquid mixtures of 2-methoxyethanol (MEL) + *n*-butylamine (NBA), + *sec*-butylamine (SBA), + *tert*-butylamine (TBA), + *n*-hexylamine (NHA), + *n*-octylamine (NOA) and + cyclohexylamine (CHA) have been measured at 308.15 K. From the experimental results the excess molar volume (V^E), excess viscosities (η^E), and excess molar Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}) have been computed as a function of composition. The parameter d^I of the Grunberg and Nissan expression has been computed. The values of V^E are negative whereas the values of η^E , G^{*E} and d^I are positive. Deviations from the ideal behaviour are discussed from the point of view of the molecular interactions present between the unlike molecules. The strength of these interactions is related with the chain length of the amines. The results are discussed in terms of the theories of non-electrolyte solutions.

Viscosities and densities for the binary liquid mixtures of 2-methoxyethanol with a number of amines have been taken up for the first time for measurements. The results obtained for the systems of 2-methoxyethanol (MEL) + *n*-butylamine (NBA), + *sec*-butylamine (SBA), + *tert*-butylamine (TBA), + *n*-hexylamine (NHA), + *n*-octylamine (NOA) and + cyclohexylamine (CHA) are reported in this paper.

Densities and viscosities of the systems mentioned were measured at 308.15 K. Excess functions like, excess molar volume (V^E), excess viscosities (η^E), excess molar free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}) and Grunberg and Nissan interaction parameter (d^I) were calculated from the experimental results at different mole fractions of 2-methoxyethanol. The values obtained are discussed in terms of molecular interactions.

Results and discussion

The excess functions η^E and V^E , Grunberg and Nissan interaction parameter d^I and the Gibbs free energy for activation of viscous flow G^{*E} were calculated from the equations,

$$\eta^E = \eta - [x_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \eta_2] \quad (1)$$

$$V^E = V - [x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2] \quad (2)$$

$$\ln \eta = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 d^I \quad (3)$$

$$G^{*E} = RT [\ln \eta V - (x_1 \ln \eta_1 V_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 V_2)] \quad (4)$$

The molar volume V of a mixture is calculated using

$$V = M/\rho \quad (5)$$

where $M = x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2$

x is the mole fraction of component 1; M_1 and M_2 are molecular weights of components 1 and 2 respectively.

The measured density (ρ) and viscosity (η) data for mixtures of 2-methoxyethanol (MEL) + *n*-butylamine (NBA), + *sec*-butylamine (SBA), + *tert*-butylamine (TBA), + *n*-hexylamine (NHA), + *n*-octylamine (NOA) and + cyclohexylamine (CHA) are used to calculate the excess molar volume (V^E), excess viscosity (η^E), excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}) and Grunberg and Nissan interaction parameter (d^I) and the results are presented in Table I.

The excess quantities (V^E , η^E and G^{*E}) have been fitted to the Redlich-Kister¹ equation by the method of least squares using the Marquardt algorithm² to derive the binary coefficient, A_J , and standard deviation, σ .

$$V^E(\Delta Y) = x_1 x_2 \sum_{J=1}^k A_{J-1} (x_2 - x_1)^{J-1} \quad (6)$$

In each case, the optimum number of coefficients, A_J was ascertained from an examination of the variation of the standard deviation, σ , with

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$$\sigma = \left[\frac{Y_{\text{cal}}^{\dagger} - Y_{\text{obs}}^{\dagger}}{n - m} \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where n represents the number of measurements and m the number of coefficients. The estimated values of A_j and σ for V^E , η^E and G^E are summarized for all the mixtures in

Table 2. In all the cases, the best fit was obtained by using only three fitting coefficients for all the mixtures.

The variation of these parameters V^E , η^E and G^{*E} with mole fraction of MEL (x_{MEL}) for the systems under study are graphically shown in Figs. 1 to 3 respectively.

It is observed that greater viscosity is obtained in MEL

Table 1. Values of density (ρ), viscosity (η), excess viscosity (η^E), excess molar volume (V^E), excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}) and Grunberg-Nissan interaction parameter (d^I) for the binary liquid mixtures of 2-methoxyethanol (MEL) + amines at 308.15 K

Mole fraction of MEL x_{MEL}	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ kg m ⁻³	$\eta \times 10^3$ kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$\eta^E \times 10^3$ kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$V^E \times 10^6$ m ³ mol ⁻¹	$G^{*E} \times 10^3$ N mol ⁻¹	d^I
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>n</i> -butylamine						
0.0000	0.7239	0.4249	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
0.1234	0.7510	0.5285	0.0043	-0.5414	51.69	0.8051
0.2404	0.7786	0.6274	0.0091	-1.0839	78.28	0.7356
0.3516	0.8059	0.7219	0.0141	-1.5293	89.51	0.6864
0.4576	0.8316	0.8199	0.0268	-1.7477	97.16	0.6896
0.5606	0.8563	0.9142	0.0382	-1.7903	96.25	0.6925
0.6503	0.8768	0.9868	0.0387	-1.6267	85.31	0.6670
0.7471	0.8956	1.0480	0.0220	-1.0501	62.49	0.5769
0.8351	0.9144	1.1106	0.0138	-0.6280	42.85	0.5338
0.9193	0.9345	1.1735	0.0089	-0.3535	22.65	0.5275
1.0000	0.9534	1.2295	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>sec</i> -butylamine						
0.0000	0.7083	0.3996	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
0.1256	0.7399	0.5105	0.0067	-0.9634	59.73	0.9450
0.2443	0.7697	0.6223	0.0201	-1.5710	96.77	0.9123
0.3566	0.7999	0.7355	0.0402	-2.1460	118.72	0.9124
0.4630	0.8285	0.8498	0.0664	-2.4736	131.81	0.9420
0.5640	0.8555	0.9507	0.0835	-2.5949	129.74	0.9471
0.6599	0.8818	1.0154	0.0681	-2.6330	102.95	0.8508
0.7511	0.9022	1.0659	0.0432	-2.1215	72.47	0.7327
0.8380	0.9214	1.1207	0.0256	-1.5459	46.26	0.6588
0.9209	0.9364	1.1750	0.0111	-0.6552	23.34	0.5981
1.0000	0.9534	1.2295	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>tert</i> -butylamine						
0.0000	0.6812	0.4126	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
0.1300	0.7169	0.5293	0.0105	-1.2285	61.15	0.9474
0.2516	0.7494	0.6631	0.0454	-1.8460	115.78	1.0609
0.3656	0.7817	0.7913	0.0802	-2.3475	145.45	1.0867
0.4727	0.8131	0.9167	0.1181	-2.6737	161.86	1.1323
0.5735	0.8433	1.0351	0.1545	-2.8259	167.27	1.2005
0.6668	0.8720	1.0832	0.1259	-2.8596	131.39	1.0675
0.7583	0.8973	1.1151	0.0832	-2.4657	89.28	0.9072
0.8432	0.9191	1.1524	0.0512	-1.8460	55.41	0.8053
0.9237	0.9363	1.1872	0.0203	-0.8855	24.99	0.6855
1.0000	0.9534	1.2295	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-

Table-1 (contd.)

2-Methoxyethanol + <i>n</i> -hexylamine						
0.0000	0.7522	0.6000	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
0.1567	0.7819	0.8278	0.1292	-1.5657	130.37	1.5851
0.2965	0.8084	1.0589	0.2723	-2.3343	221.52	1.7038
0.4194	0.8339	1.2451	0.3811	-2.8550	266.52	1.7627
0.5291	0.8578	1.3815	0.4484	-3.0918	280.87	1.8241
0.6276	0.8817	1.4558	0.4607	-3.2843	266.87	1.8663
0.7166	0.9032	1.4589	0.4078	-3.1947	226.54	1.8439
0.7973	0.9176	1.4338	0.3319	-2.4323	181.48	1.8513
0.8708	0.9302	1.3969	0.2487	-1.5923	134.28	1.9588
0.9382	0.9401	1.3384	0.1478	-0.6022	80.33	2.2288
1.0000	0.9534	1.2295	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>n</i> -octylamine						
0.0000	0.7702	0.9267	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
0.1894	0.8012	1.2751	0.2910	-2.3910	175.04	1.7303
0.3445	0.8286	1.4741	0.4431	-3.6108	243.09	1.6245
0.4739	0.8524	1.6139	0.5437	-4.0311	278.53	1.6881
0.5835	0.8756	1.6673	0.5639	-4.2745	277.64	1.7382
0.6777	0.8945	1.6698	0.5379	-3.9534	260.00	1.8189
0.7592	0.9089	1.6086	0.4520	-3.1992	221.19	1.8428
0.8307	0.9216	1.5561	0.3779	-2.3790	185.77	2.0158
0.8937	0.9346	1.4815	0.2842	-1.7027	140.28	2.2794
0.9498	0.9436	1.3789	0.1646	-0.7606	83.52	2.7033
1.0000	0.9534	1.2295	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
2-Methoxyethanol + cyclohexylamine						
0.0000	0.8527	1.3249	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-
0.1393	0.8660	1.3136	0.0021	-0.4153	3.59	0.0154
0.2670	0.8781	1.3034	0.0042	-0.6386	6.51	0.0184
0.3844	0.8893	1.2982	0.0104	-0.7353	10.63	0.0354
0.4927	0.9000	1.2899	0.0123	-0.7677	12.12	0.0402
0.5930	0.9104	1.2943	0.0262	-0.7647	18.53	0.0868
0.6861	0.9198	1.2834	0.0241	-0.6630	17.20	0.0903
0.7727	0.9286	1.2632	0.0123	-0.5137	10.71	0.0573
¹ 0.8536	0.9372	1.2535	0.0107	-0.3576	8.48	0.0672
0.9291	0.9456	1.2423	0.0062	-0.1985	4.81	0.0768
1.0000	0.9534	1.2295	0.0000	0.0000	0.00	-

rich region and is in consistence with the idea that the molecules of MEL are strongly self-associated. It is further observed that the viscosity of these mixtures varied non-linearly with increase in x_{MEL} .

It is clear from the Fig. 1 that the negative V^E values are obtained over the entire composition range for all these systems which indicates the presence of strong molecular interactions between the components of the mixture. It is also observed from the Fig. 1 and Table 1 that the negative V^E

values fall in the sequence.

From Fig. 1, it is further observed that V^E values become more negative as the chain length in amines increase. The negative V^E vs x_{MEL} plots were found to be large and unsymmetrical with maxima between 0.5 to 0.6 mole fractions of MEL.

Several effects may contribute to the value of V^E and

Fig. 1. Plots of excess molar volume (V^E) vs mole fraction of 2-methoxyethanol (x_{MEL}) at 308.15 K for the binary mixtures of MEL with NBA (\blacksquare), SBA (\square), TBA (\blacktriangle), NHA (\bullet), NOA (\circ) and CHA (Δ).

three different effects may be considered as being important : (a) break up of hydrogen bonds and dipolar interactions in MEL and intermolecular hydrogen bonded interactions in amines, (b) interstitial accommodation of one component into the other and (c) the possible hydrogen bond interactions between unlike molecules. The actual volume change would, therefore, depend on the relative strength of these three opposing effects.

Several workers^{3,4} reported negative excess volumes for the mixtures of MEL with polar components. This observation is supported by the present work where V^E values are negative for all the amines. The negative excess volumes reported by Subha *et al.*⁵ were shown to be due to the interaction between the oxygen atom of MEL and hydrogen atom of other component. The interaction between MEL and amines due to the formation of strong intermolecular hydrogen bonded complexes would produce negative excess volume. From Fig. 1 it is clear that the negative excess volumes increase in magnitude as the alkyl group of the normal amines become large and they fall in the following order : CHA < NBA < NHA < NOA. The effect of interaction between the two components becomes more and more predominant as the alkyl group of the normal amines increase in size due to their electron donating ability.

It is further observed from Fig. 1 that the negative V^E values increased with increase in branching of amines and they are in the following order : *n*-butylamine < *sec*-butylamine < *tert*-butylamine.

In the case of branched amines the excess volumes are higher than the respective normal amines. It is also observed that in the case of cyclohexylamine the excess volume is less negative than the corresponding *n*-hexylamine. This abnormal behaviour of the branched and cyclic amines may be due to the steric factors. Similar observations were made by Pal and Singh⁶ in the case of V^E values of 2-methoxy ethanol mixtures with different 2-(2-alkoxy ethoxy) ethanols. They have attributed the behaviour primarily due to the steric factors arising from a change in the proportion of different structural forms of 2-methoxy ethanol molecules with a change in its mole fraction.

Thus, in the present study the negative V^E values for MEL + amines indicate the predominance of hydrogen bonding interactions between them over the other effects.

Fig. 2 shows that η^E values are positive for the whole composition range for all the systems under study. A correlation between signs of η^E and V^E has been observed for a number of binary solvent systems^{7,8}, η^E being positive where V^E is negative or vice-versa. In general for systems,

Fig. 2. Plots of excess molar volume (η^E) vs mole fraction of 2-methoxyethanol (x_{MEL}) at 308.15 K for the binary mixtures of MEL with NBA (\blacksquare), SBA (\square), TBA (\blacktriangle), NHA (\bullet), NOA (\circ) and CHA (Δ).

Table 2. Estimated parameters of eq. (6) for excess functions of the binary mixtures of 2-methoxyethanol + amines at 308.15 K

Function	A_0	A_1	A_2	σ
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>n</i> -butylamine				
$V^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-7.180	-0.142	4.731	0.070
$\eta^E \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	0.127	-0.085	-0.128	0.005
$G^{*E} \times 10^3$ (N mol ⁻¹)	148.860	57.030	111.290	1.387
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>sec</i> -butylamine				
$V^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-10.253	2.628	1.373	0.126
$\eta^E \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	0.284	-0.134	-0.363	0.007
$G^{*E} \times 10^3$ (N mol ⁻¹)	28.083	42.070	-130.120	3.985
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>tert</i> -butylamine				
$V^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-11.047	3.088	-1.868	0.108
$\eta^E \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	0.522	-0.264	-0.612	0.012
$G^{*E} \times 10^3$ (N mol ⁻¹)	114.340	-8.401	107.670	1.907
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>n</i> -hexylamine				
$V^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-12.744	3.340	-0.190	0.218
$\eta^E \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	1.729	-0.878	-0.334	0.011
$G^{*E} \times 10^3$ (N mol ⁻¹)	23.959	13.689	172.320	2.188
2-Methoxyethanol + <i>n</i> -octylamine				
$V^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-16.879	2.044	1.451	0.113
$\eta^E \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	2.176	-0.679	-0.300	0.015
$G^{*E} \times 10^3$ (N mol ⁻¹)	-71.701	-61.196	47.013	1.085
2-Methoxyethanol + cyclohexylamine				
$V^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-3.102	0.275	-0.080	0.017
$\eta^E \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	0.070	-0.073	-0.055	0.005
$G^{*E} \times 10^3$ (N mol ⁻¹)	101.860	-26.656	138.370	1.879

where dispersion and dipolar interactions are operating η^E values are found to be negative, whereas charge transfer and hydrogen bonding interactions lead to the formation of complex species between unlike molecules there by resulting in positive η^E values⁹.

The algebraic values of η^E for all the mixtures of MEL + amines fall in the order : CHA < NBA < SBA < TBA < NHA < NOA.

This order suggests that hydrogen bonding between unlike molecules increase with increase in chain length in amines. A similar observation was reported by Krishnaiah *et al.*¹⁰.

It has been reported^{11,12} that G^{*E} parameter can be considered as a reliable criterion to detect or exclude the presence of interactions between unlike molecules. According to these authors, the magnitude of the positive values is an excellent indicator of the strength of specific interactions. G^{*E} values for the systems under study suggest the following order : CHA < NBA < SBA < TBA < NHA < NOA.

The above order is in accordance with the viscosity results of these mixtures explained above. Similar behaviour was reported by Krishnaiah *et al.*¹⁰ in case of G^{*E} values for mixtures of 2-alkoxyethanols in water.

Fort and Moore¹³ and Ramamoorthy^{14,15} reported that for any binary liquid mixture, the positive value of d^I indicates the presence of strong interactions and the negative value of d^I indicates the presence of weak interactions between the components. On this basis the positive d^I values obtained in the present study for all the six systems (*cf.* Table 1) confirms the presence of strong interactions between the component molecules. A similar observation was made by Subha *et al.*¹⁶ from the d^I values of the binary liquid mixtures of propionic acid with alcohols.

In conclusion, it may be said that the observed variation of the properties of the mixtures studied support the view that the interactions between unlike molecules is predominant and characterized by the negative V^E and positive η^E , G^{*E} and d^I values.

Fig. 3. Plots of Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^*E) vs mole fraction of 2-methoxyethanol (x_{MEL}) at 308.15 K for the binary mixtures of MEL with NBA (■), SBA (□), TBA (▲), NHA (●), NOA (○) and CHA (Δ).

Experimental

Density was measured using bicapillary pycnometer having a capillary diameter of 0.85 mm, which was calibrated using double-distilled water. The necessary buoyancy corrections were applied. The density values were reproducible within $\pm 0.2 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. A thermostatically controlled, well-stirred constant temperature water bath, Schott-Gerate (Model CT 050/2 made in Germany) whose temperature was controlled to $\pm 0.02 \text{ K}$ was used for all measurements.

Viscosity was measured using an Ubbelohde viscometer. The time of efflux of a constant volume of liquid through the capillary was measured with the help of a pre calibrated ROCAR stop watch capable of recording $\pm 0.1 \text{ s}$. The viscometer was kept vertical in a thermostat at 308.15 K. The efflux time for the water at 308.15 K was about 302 s. The flow time of pure liquids and liquid mixtures were measured a number of times and the average of the read-

ings was taken. The viscosity was calculated from the average of efflux time t and density ρ according to :

$$\eta/\rho = at - b/t$$

where a and b are the characteristic constants of the viscometer. These were determined by taking water and benzene as calibrating liquids. The kinetic energy corrections were calibrated from these values and they were found negligible. The viscosity measurements were accurate to $\pm 0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Methoxyethanol and all the amines used were purchased from E. Merck and were used as purchased. Mixtures were prepared by mixing weighed amounts of the pure liquids adopting the method of closed system, by using Mettler balance with precision of $\pm 0.1 \text{ mg}$. The measurements were made with proper care in an AC room to avoid evaporation losses.

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